

Mean and variation based fuzzy characterization of Young's modulus of a flax/epoxy biocomposite material

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1 Introduction

In addition to be recyclable, natural fiber composites (NFC) have interesting mechanical properties and compete with non-degradable materials in several fields of application. Indeed they present low density, good mechanical properties, low cost, and ease of machining. However the disparity of their properties, which results in variability of their behavior, prevents the growth of their use, unlike synthetic fiber composites.

To assess their sustainability and promote the use of these materials in the industry, their mechanical behavior must be carefully studied. Prediction models use several parameters that are often measured with uncertainty. Furthermore, these parameters differ depending on the various tools and / or standards used.

Lord and Morelle [1] conducted a study to identify the sources of uncertainty in the calculation of the modulus of elasticity. They demonstrated that the uncertainties in Young's modulus values can vary from 1% to 6%.

The objectives in this work are twofold. Firstly it is desired to implement a fabrication protocol for a commercial flax/epoxy eco-composite prepreg. Secondly a study of the capacity of a fuzzy model to reconcile its elastic properties obtained by different techniques (namely by tensile and acoustic test according to ISO and ASTM standards) will be conducted.

2 Material and method

2.1 Prepreg characteristics

In order to evaluate the elastic properties of the material under study, plates with the dimension of 30 cm x 25 cm were molded.

Flax/epoxy prepreps plane weave (Fig. 1) from LINEO NV «FlaxPreg BL 150» were used for manufacturing of the plates. The characteristics of this weave are summarized in the Tab.1.

Fig.1. Prepreg weave roll «FlaxPreg BL150»

Fiber fraction	By weight m_f	50%
	By volume V_f	45%
Warp to weft ratio	1/1	
Fiber density ρ_f (g/cm³)	1.45	
Weight of flax M_s (g/m²)	150g of weave/m ²	
Theoretical density of tissue ρ_c (g/cm³)	1.31	

Tab. 1. Characteristics of «FlaxPreg BL 150»

2.2 Composites fabrication

Manual cutting and stacking of uncured prepreps were made in two orientations: ten successive stacks in the weft direction [T]₁₀ and ten stacks diagonally [± 45]_{5s}. The laminates were manufactured in a thermo hydraulic press at pressures of 2 and 4 bars.

Fig. 2 shows the cure and pressure cycles applied during the plates manufacturing.

Fig.2. Processing cycle applied during plate manufacturing.

2.3 Specimen cutting

The cutting of plates was made with a diamond blade cooled by water to avoid burning of the fibers. The geometric dimensions of the specimens meet the standards in ISO527-4 [2] and ASTM D3039 [5] for tensile tests and ASTM E 1876-09 [3] for acoustic impulse test. The dimensions of these rectangular specimens are 250mm × 15mm × 2.4mm. Tab. 2 shows the characteristics of each set of specimens. The fiber content is calculated according to ASTM D3171-99 [4] with the following equation:

$$V_F = n \times M_s / (\rho_f \times h) \quad (1)$$

Specimens	[±45] _{5S}	[T] ₁₀
Identifier	FE45	FE90
Thickness h (mm)	2.4	2.4
V _f (%)	43%	43%
Density (g/cm ³)	1.11	1.12

Tab. 2. Characteristics of two stacking sequences

2.4 Experimentation

2.4.1 Acoustic impulse test in flexural mode

Considering non-destructiveness of acoustic impulse test, this method was carried out first in order to use the same samples in the tensile test method. Five specimens were randomly selected among all specimens fabricated for this study. Each specimen is placed between two strings and excited by an automated tapping device (Fig.3). The vibration signals emitted by the specimen are captured by a microphone and transmitted to a signal processing software “Resonant Frequency & Damping Analyzer (RFDA)”. It uses Fast Fourier Transform algorithms to measure the resonant frequencies and internal friction of the tested specimens at room temperature.

Fig. 3. IMCE RFDA acoustic impulse instrument.

From the fundamental resonant frequency found by the signal processing software, and knowing the dimensions and mass of the specimens, the Young's modulus can be derived according to the following equation [3]:

$$E = 0.9465 \left(\frac{m f_f^2}{b} \right) \left(\frac{L^3}{t^3} \right) T_1 \quad (2)$$

where :

E = Young modulus (Pa)

m = masse of the bar (gr)

b = width of the bar (mm)

L = length of the bar (mm)

t = thickness of the bar (mm)

f_f = fundamental resonant frequency of bar (Hz)

T_1 = correction factor for fundamental flexural mode and for $L/t \geq 20$ it is given by:

$$T_1 = [1 + 6.585(t/L)^2] \quad (3)$$

2.4.2 Monotonic tensile tests at room temperature

The same five samples used to make acoustic tests are selected to do monotonic tensile tests at ambient laboratory conditions. These tests were performed following ISO 527-4 test conditions for isotropic and orthotropic fiber-reinforced plastic composites [2] and ASTM D3039 test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials [5]. The tensile tests were performed using an Instron model LM-U150 electromechanical testing machine, equipped with a 150 kN load cell and connected to extensometer of 50 mm to register the strain during the test. A crosshead speed of 2 mm/min was used according with ISO 527 and ASTM D3039. Using the stress-strain data acquired digitally, the Young's modulus is obtained by the relation $E = \Delta\sigma / \Delta\varepsilon$ in the range of appropriate values for strain according to the given standard, i.e. between 0.0005 and 0.0025 for the ISO-527 standard and between 0.001-0.003 for the ASTM D3039 standard.

The accuracy of these measurements is affected by several uncertainties: dimensions of the specimens, values recorded by the extensometer and load cell, alignment of the grips and fixtures, number of points recorded for analysis, etc. Such variability, along with the different range of appropriate values for strain according to ISO and ASTM standards, affect the choice of the final value for the elastic modulus of the material.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Acoustic impulse

The summary data of the mechanical properties recorded by RFDA is presented in Tab. 3.

Specimen	Frequency (Hz) (C _v)	E (GPa) (C _v)
FE90	127,35±1.08 (0,008)	12,93±0.23 (0.02)
FE45	83,47±2,86 (0,031)	4,88 ±0.10 (0,020)

Tab.3. Acoustic impulse characteristics of each specimen

Each value is an average of five measurements. The resonant frequency is identified using the spectra of two strikes mode: flexural and torsional vibration mode. Once the fundamental frequencies of each test-piece are determined, ASTM E 1876-09 [3] standard method is used to calculate Young

modulus. The uncertainty of the modulus is partly due to the difference of the mass and physical size of test-pieces.

Fig. 4 represents the frequency spectrum of FE45N1 specimen in flexural mode (blue curve) and flexural/torsional mode (red curve). It shows the fundamental frequency (a stronger response) at 85,83Hz, plus a series of harmonics: second harmonic at 240 Hz, third harmonic at 478 Hz and a fifth mode at 1220Hz. In addition a new peak was observed at 801 Hz in flexural mode.

Fig.4. Frequency spectrum of FE45N1 tested in flexural mode and flexural-torsional mode

3.2 Monotonic tensile test

Analysis is made based on the evolution of the stress versus strain (Fig.5). Both types of tested specimens go through a first linear elastic phase characterized by an elastic modulus E. Then, the curve loses its initial linearity (damage of the composite is started). In the last phase the specimen finds a linear behavior up to its final rupture.

The difference in behavior between the two types of specimens FE90 and FE45 in the last step or change in the slope of the stress / strain curve (the non-linearity) is very important to their rupture [6]. This nonlinearity is due to damage of the composite and viscoelastic behavior of the epoxy matrix. The summary of results for the tensile tests is shown in Tab. 4.

Fig.5. Stress/strain diagrams, top $[\pm 45]_{5s}$, bottom $[T]_{10}$

Specimens	FE45 (C_v)	FE90 (C_v)
E_T (GPa) ASTM D3039 (C_v)	$4,79 \pm 0,27$ (0,056)	$12,23 \pm 0,64$ (0,054)
E_T (GPa) ISO 527-4 (C_v)	$4,77 \pm 0,41$ (0,086)	$12,68 \pm 0,95$ (0,075)
σ_R (MPa)	$76,8 \pm 3,23$	$162,30 \pm 3,13$
ε_R (%)	$5,58 \pm 0,20$	$1,78 \pm 0,04$

Tab.4. Monotonic tensile test characteristics of each specimen according to two different standards

Fig.6. Young's modulus of the sample FE90 (top) and FE45 (bottom) according to ASTM 1876, ISO 527-4 and ASTM D3039 standards

Fig. 6 summarizes the data to be reconciled. As can be seen there is a variation in the elastic modulus of around 2.52 GPa (11.1 to 13.62) for the samples in the weft direction and of 1.15 GPa (from 4 to 5.15) for specimens with fiber orientation at 45°

4 Fuzzy modeling

4.1 Mean model

Fig. 7 shows the generic format of the fuzzy model when only the input mean is considered (here the “mean model” refers to a model without any reference to the variability inherent to each testing method).

Fig.7. generic format of the inputs and output of the mean fuzzy model

The numerical values of the elastic modulus obtained by tensile and acoustic impulse tests according to the ISO and ASTM standards are used as inputs of the fuzzy model. In particular an input modulus of elasticity is transformed into linguistic values with three fuzzy sets: small, average and large. For each type of specimen, the total range of these fuzzy sets is between the minimum and maximum value of the elastic modulus obtained for these specimens. These inputs and the output are related by nine rules, a sample of which is shown here for acoustic impulse:

- If ($E_{Impulsion}$ is small) then (E_{final} is small)
- If ($E_{Impulsion}$ is average) then (E_{final} is average)
- If ($E_{Impulsion}$ is large) then (E_{final} is large)

The rules for tensile tests with ISO and ASTM standards are formulated similarly.

4.2 Mean and variation model

In order to include the notion of the confidence one has in these input values, which reflects the variability inherent to the different measurement techniques and standards used, another important input, namely the coefficient of variation for each module of elasticity, was included in another fuzzy model (Fig. 8.)

Fig.8. generic format of the inputs and output of the mean and variation fuzzy model

The coefficients of variation for each method are transformed into a single linguistic value using a spline-based membership function. The membership functions of the coefficients of variation are between 0 (more confidence) and the value of coefficients of variation of each method (less confidence).

The output of the fuzzy model is divided into nine fuzzy sets, namely the minimum and maximum values corresponding to the minimum and maximum values of Young's modulus obtained from the three different methods.

The inputs and the output are related by nine rules, a sample of which is shown here for acoustic impulse:

- If ($E_{Impulsion}$ is small and $C_{V, Impulsion}$ is small) then (E_{final} is small)
- If ($E_{Impulsion}$ is average and $C_{V, Impulsion}$ is small) then (E_{final} is average)
- If ($E_{Impulsion}$ is large and $C_{V, Impulsion}$ is small) then (E_{final} is large)

The rules for tensile tests with ISO and ASTM standards are formulated similarly.

For both models the center of gravity method was used for the defuzzification process.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Mean model

The FE45 samples will be used for investigation. The statistical average of all 5 specimens using the three testing methods and standards stands at 4.81 GPa. On the other hand a value of 4.59 GPa is obtained when using the fuzzy model with all three inputs at the middle of their range, i.e when all inputs have a 100% membership to the fuzzy set "average". Table 5 shows the values obtained for other combinations of inputs.

$E_{impulse}$	E_{ISO}	E_{ASTM}	Fuzzy output
4,84 (average)	4,58 (average)	4,68 (average)	4,59
4,7 (small)	4,0 (small)	4,3 (small)	4,35
4,7 (small)	4,58 (average)	5,06 (large)	4,63
4,7 (small)	4,58 (average)	4,3 (small)	4,57
4,97 (large)	5,15 (large)	5,06 (large)	4,96

Tab.5. Some results of the mean fuzzy model

Fig. 9 to 11 show the E_{final} response as a function of a combination of two modules while the third is kept at the middle of its interval (i.e. 100% membership to its “average” fuzzy set).

Fig. 9. E_{final} as a function of ISO and impulse test values, mean model

Fig. 10. E_{final} as a function of ASTM and impulse test values, mean model

Fig.11. E_{final} as a function of ISO and ASTM test values, mean model

In Fig. 9 and 10 it can be seen that the values for the impulse test influence the final result in a rather narrow area corresponding to the smaller interval in which the values of this test lie. This influence is also of a rather small magnitude.

On the other hand the tensile tests span a larger interval and their interactions are therefore effective in pretty much the whole range of values (Fig. 11).

5.2 Mean and variation model

5.2.1 Output behavior for each method

The idea here is to reconcile Young’s modulus by not only looking at the mean values obtained from different testing methods but also by looking at the variability inherent to the method, hence giving more “confidence” to inputs that present less variability (lower values of C_v).

Fig. 12 to 14 show the E_{final} response as a function of the modules and coefficient of variation of each type of test (all other values are kept at the middle of their intervals). For each type of test one can clearly see how its influence on the final value vanishes when its corresponding C_v increases.

Fig.12. Mean and variation model, acoustic impulse

Fig.13. Mean and variation model, ISO tensile test

Fig.14. Mean and variation model, ASTM tensile test

For example in Fig. 12, as soon as the C_v reaches the middle of its interval then the influence of the impulsion test value disappears (recall that all other values are kept at the middle of their intervals in this particular case, this behavior can of course change if the other variables are kept at different values).

$E_{impulse}$	E_{ISO}	E_{ASTM}	Fuzzy output
4,84 (average)	4,58 (average)	4,68 (average)	4,73
4,7 (small)	4,0 (small)	4,3 (small)	4,62
4,7 (small)	4,58 (average)	5,06 (large)	4,82
4,7 (small)	4,58 (average)	4,3 (small)	4,62
4,97 (large)	5,15 (large)	5,06 (large)	4,91

Tab.6. Some results of the mean and variation fuzzy model (same combinations as Tab. 5)

5.2.2 Output behavior for combined methods

Tab. 6 presents the same combinations of values as those of table 5, with all three C_v kept at the values reported in tables 3 and 4. As can be seen, because the impulse test has a lower C_v , the values returned by the model are generally dragged towards those of this particular test, with a slight influence of the ASTM tensile test which also has a lower C_v than the ISO tensile test. An interesting result is that of the last row. The value returned by the model is

lower than all those used as inputs. This counter intuitive result highlights how this particular model becomes limited when the inputs all lie at their maximum boundaries. Note that a similar limitation also appears in the last row in table 5.

Fig. 15 to 17 show the E_{final} response as a function of combination of modules while keeping the C_v at the values obtained in tables 3 and 4.

As can be seen in Fig. 15 the impulse test method drives completely the response because of its much lower C_v compared to that of the ISO tensile results. This is completely opposite to the result in Fig. 9, hence showing the importance of the variability in the results.

In Fig. 16 a similar observation holds but with less drive from the impulse test since the ASTM tensile test has a C_v that is closer to that of the impulse test.

Fig.15. E_{final} as a function of ISO tensile and impulse test values, mean and variation model

Fig.16. E_{final} as a function of ASTM tensile and impulse test values, mean and variation model

Fig.17. E_{final} as a function of ASTM and ISO tensile test values, mean and variation model

Finally in figure 17 the same observation holds: since the C_v of the ASTM tensile test is lower than that of the ISO tensile test, then the influence of the latter is negligible. Once again, comparing this result with that of figure 11 clearly shows how variability plays an important role in the computation of the reconciled module value.

6 Conclusions

In this work, two types of laminated NFC made of commercial flax/epoxy, identified by FE45 and FE90 in this paper, were manufactured by thermal compression.

Samples were cut from plates and tested by a non-destructive acoustic impulse method to evaluate their Young's modulus. Destructive tensile tests were also performed later on the same specimens to evaluate their mechanical properties in monotonic tension as per ISO and ASTM standards.

The results show a certain level of variability in the values of Young's modulus obtained by the different techniques and/or standards. It was therefore proposed to develop a model that reconciles these values rather than calculating a simple average value, in hope to obtain a more representative and reliable module that could be useful for evaluating the performance of such materials, or for further study of eventual structures that can be made from them.

Fuzzy logic was chosen as the modeling method. Continuous models of the reconciled value of the elastic modulus could be obtained that also take into consideration the variability of the measurements. In this paper such variation was included in the form of the measured coefficient of variation inherent to each test method.

The results obtained show how the model adapts simultaneously to the mean and C_v values of each type of test. Generally speaking, if a user inputs a larger mean value and lower C_v for any of the three methods used in the model, then the fuzzy sets of this method should cover a larger portion of the defuzzified output, hence making the "weight" of this input predominant compared to the other ones.

Future work includes building fuzzy models with larger sets of data, for example using other types of NFC or samples with different ply orientations. Further investigations could also be oriented towards the comparative study of the results obtained using different configurations of the developed fuzzy model (fuzzification methods, inference method, defuzzification method, etc).

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